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Case Report

SPURIOUS TSH ELEVATION IN A RIG FED PATIENT**Sharon Wilson¹, Rimal John Roy², Dr. S.K Mathew³, Dr. Dhanu Josey⁴**^{1,2} PharmD Intern , Nazareth College of Pharmacy, Othara, Tiruvalla³ Emeritus Professor, Department of General Medicine, Believers Church Medical College Hospital, Thiruvalla⁴ Clinical Specialist , Department of General medicine , Believers Church Medical College Hospital, Thiruvalla**Abstract:**

Spurious TSH elevation refers to an increase in TSH levels that does not correspond to the clinical hormone levels of hypothyroidism , often caused by factors such as improper medication administration. Proper timing and administration of thyroxine replacement are essential for maintaining accurate thyroid hormone levels.

In this case, we present a patient who experienced a falsely elevated TSH level due to improper administration of thyroid medication via a feeding tube (Radiologically Inserted Gastrostomy feed). An intervention was made to adjust the administration schedule, which helped correct the TSH and thyroid hormone levels.

Keywords : RIG feed , TSH , Thyroxine

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INTRODUCTION:

A Radiologically inserted gastrostomy (RIG), or percutaneous radiological gastrostomy (RPG), is a procedure where a gastrostomy tube is inserted percutaneously into the stomach under fluoroscopic guidance, principally to provide nutritional support for patients with swallowing disorders. The food and medicines can be thoroughly blended and feed is provided directly to the stomach¹.

Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in both brain and somatic development in infants, as well as in regulating metabolic activity in adults. They are essential for the proper functioning of nearly every organ system in the body. To ensure a steady supply, the thyroid gland stores large amounts of thyroid hormone. Additionally, thyroid hormone biosynthesis and secretion are tightly regulated by a feedback mechanism that is highly sensitive to even small changes in circulating hormone levels, ensuring that the body maintains optimal thyroid hormone availability². Various drugs, foods and diseases are known for interacting with Thyroxine which increases or either decrease the activity of Thyroxine results in increased or decreased TSH level^{3,4,5,6,7,8,9}.

TSH level usually increases with low thyroid hormone levels and it is a marker for adjusting Thyroid hormone replacement. Thyroxine replacement is usually administered in empty stomach prior to any oral feeds for best absorption.

CASE REPORT:

A 96 year old male patient was admitted with diagnosis of aspiration pneumonia. He is known case of total thyroidectomy- papillary carcinoma thyroid with relapse, post RAI(2019), on tracheostomy, oesophageal stenosis- s/p radiologically inserted gastrostomy, systemic hypertension, carcinoma prostate .

He was taking the following medications :Thyroxine 125mcg tablet once a day in the

morning , Tab. Lenvatinib once a day , Calcium Citrate+ Folic Acid + Vitamin D3 tablets three times a day ,Tab. Calcitriol 0.25 mg three times a day , Tab. Lemborexant 5mg on Bed time ,Tab. Melatonin 3mg on Bed time , Tab. Mucorina two times a day , Tab. thiamine 100 mg once a day in the morning, Tab. Rosuvastatin 5mg at bed time, Tab. Folic acid 5mg at noon ,glycopyrrolate tablets in the morning ,Tab. Finasteride 5mg at bed time ,Tab . Silodosin 8 mg bedtime, Tab. Cilnidipine 5 mg ,and Vitamin supplements . All the medication were given through rig feed . Most of the above listed medications were taken in morning

On October 27, 2024, the patient was found to be drowsy, though his vital signs were stable. Laboratory test showed elevated TSH level of 32 micro IU/mL. An endocrinology consultation was requested, and the recommendation was made to increase the thyroid medication dose to 150 mcg once daily. Hence dose was increased to 150mcg .But his TSH level didn't decline.

On further enquiry with the nurses it was understood that medications taken in morning are all given together including the Thyroxine tablet at the same time through the rig feed .

INTERVENTION:

Thyroid medication (T. Thyroxine 125 mcg) was recommended to be taken at 5 AM every morning, separately from all other medications. The other drugs were rescheduled to be given after 2 hours, ensuring that there is enough time for proper absorption of the thyroxine before any interactions with other drugs occur.

Hence , the dose of Thyroxine was reduced back to 125mcg once a day. After the proper administration of the thyroid medications , his TSH level decreased to 18.36 micro IU/ml. Later on TSH level reached near normal levels.

Graph1 : Variation in the TSH level before and after the interpretation

DISCUSSION:

The thyroid hormone controls metabolism, growth, and many essential body functions. Its regulation is managed through the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis, a feedback system involving the hypothalamus, anterior pituitary gland, and thyroid gland. In this system, the hypothalamus releases TRH, stimulating the pituitary to produce TSH, which in turn prompts the thyroid to release T3 and T4. These hormones then regulate their own production through negative feedback².

In critically ill or RIG-fed patients, this balance can be disrupted due to inappropriate administration of Thyroxine sometimes leading to false elevations of TSH without true thyroid dysfunction⁹.

Thyroid replacement therapy was given to this patient due to total thyroidectomy, patients TSH levels were found to be increasing. TSH levels increase due to inadequate absorption of Thyroid replacement therapy.

It is important for patients to understand how and when to take their thyroid medication. Proper timing and administration help maintain stable thyroid hormone levels and prevent the need for unnecessarily higher doses. Taking the medication correctly can improve treatment effectiveness, minimize side effects, support adherence to therapy, and reduce the risk of complications from interactions with other medications¹⁰.

Medication counselling for thyroxine is crucial in managing hypothyroidism and improving adherence to treatment. It is essential that patients and their caregivers who are on assisted feeding situation like RIG, PEG or Ryles tube should be advised on giving

the Thyroid replacement separately and as the first medication of the day, spacing from other medications or feeds. Clear understanding of the correct administration method helps achieve better control of thyroid levels, minimize complications, and enhance overall treatment effectiveness¹¹.

CONCLUSION:

This case report emphasizes the critical importance of correct thyroxine replacement therapy administration. The effectiveness of thyroid medications can be significantly affected by food, other drugs, and specific medical conditions. When patients are RIG/PEG feed clear instructions regarding Thyroid Hormone Replacement should be given to caregivers. Proper counselling plays a vital role in ensuring patients understand the correct way to take thyroid hormones. It should be taken in empty stomach, avoid mixing with other food or drugs. Establishing a strong rapport with both patients and their caregivers makes it easier to explain the timing and potential interactions, helping to minimize side effects. This approach not only improves medication adherence but also enhances the overall management of Hypothyroidism.

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